

Integrated pest management – insects

Rice grain yield loss due to rice hispa damage

P. B. Chatterjee and P. K. Bera, Rice Research Station, P.O. Chinsurah R.S. 712102, West Bengal, India

Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* Olivier appears sporadically in West Bengal ricefields. In favorable years, infestation starts on summer or boro rice and spreads to wetland (aman) rice. In most cases, population buildup and dispersal are aggregated.

We studied yield loss caused by rice hispa in an IR36 crop in boro. The crop suffered repeated waves of rice hispa

attack, beginning with transplanting in mid-Jan to harvest in Apr. Highly irregular patterns of damage were visible as white lesions in leaves. We marked 10 samples of 1 m² each that exhibited 5-80% leaf area damage. Undamaged samples were also marked. Each sample contained 35 hills.

Individual samples were separately harvested, threshed, and weighed. Yield loss caused by rice hispa in a short-duration variety like IR36 was negatively correlated ($r = 0.9927387^{**}$) with increase in leaf area damaged, and correspondingly less grain yield was recorded (see figure). ■

Effect of different degrees of rice hispa attack on grain yield.

Behavior of the wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* (Boes. et Str.)

W. L. Morrill, Entomology Research Laboratory, Montana State University, Bozeman, Montana 59717, USA; and E. G. Rubia, Entomology Department, IRR1

L. pseudoannulata is a common spider in wetland ricefields. Unlike other species, the wolf spider can hide under water. We have observed silver bubbles covering the body of a wolf spider under water. Perhaps hairs present all over the body of the spider trap air films for a period of time, allowing the spider to breathe.

We studied the factors that enable *L. pseudoannulata* to hide under water. A 35-d-old TN1 potted rice plant was placed in a 35- × 25- × 30-cm aquarium half-filled with water and covered with nylon mesh. Spiders at different stages were released one at a time and subjected to the following conditions: light change, splashing water, plant movement, and physical injury.

For light change, the aquarium was covered with black muslin for 5 min, then the cloth was slowly removed. The change from darkness to light did not affect the spiders, except for a female carrying an egg sac and a spiderling (see table). These moved up near the junction of the leaves and stems.

Time spent under water by *Lycosa pseudoannulata*.^a

Condition	Time range (min)		
	Spiderling	Adult	
		Male	Female
Light change	0	0	0
Splashing water	0	0	0
Tapping rice plant	0	0	2.35-13.09
Physical injury	1.33-10.15	-	3.25- 8.59

^an=12.

Splashing water on the rice plant caused all spiders to move up and down the rice plant or away from the rice plant, if they were hit by water. This has also been observed in ricefields during spider collection.

Tapping the rice plant caused early-instar spiderlings and newly molted male spiders to move up and down the rice plant or to hide at the base in between tillers. A female spider carrying an egg sac went under water 4 out of 11 times the plant was tapped. Duration of her stay under water ranged from 3 to 13 min.

Pinching a leg using forceps caused a newly molted male and a female with egg sac to go under water for 1-10 min.

The underwater hiding behavior explains why some sampling methods, such as D-vac, are not efficient in collecting the wolf spider in ricefields. Air coming from a D-vac machine

disturbs the canopy and the spiders dive. The FARMCOP sampling device does not disturb the spiders so much, although sometimes we had to wait for spiders to emerge. ■

Alternate plant hosts of rice leaffolder (LF)

L. R. Bharati, Hari Om, and K. S. Kushwaha, Haryana Agricultural University (HAU), Rice Research Station (RRS), Kaul 132021 Haryana, India

LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) was a minor and sporadic pest in Haryana until 1986. Epidemics occurred in 1987 and 1989 wet seasons.

Annual or perennial plant habitats that influence LF number are important in understanding epidemic patterns. It is also essential to establish the relative suitability of wild or cultivated hosts that contribute to LF carryover from Nov to May, when rice is not grown, as a basis for a sound integrated pest management strategy.

The normal cropping pattern in the region is rice - wheat. We found that rice LF could survive winter on wheat. Under fluctuating temperatures in the screen-house (max 23.5 °C and min 8.7 °C with 4-30 °C range) from Nov to the first week of Mar, rice LF completed one generation

on wheat. Incubation, larval, and pupal periods lasted 5, 94-96, and 33-35 d, respectively. Total development period from egg to adult emergence was 132-136 d. Pupation was 30%.

We surveyed rice-growing areas in Sep 1989 to locate other alternate hosts. LF was found on nine host plants of Gramineae family and the order Graminales: *Agropyron repens* (L.)

Beauv., *Brachiaria mutica* (Forsk.) Stapf., *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Beauv., *Digitaria sanguinalis* (L.) Scop., *D. setigera* Roth ex R&S, *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link., *E. crus-galli* L., *Saccharum munjo* L., and *Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers.

All hosts except *B. mutica*, *E. colona*, and *E. crus-galli* were not known before. Larvae were found

feeding on these hosts in and alongside the ricefields. The perennial weed *A. repens* was most preferred (85% damaged leaves), followed by *E. crus-galli*, *S. halepense*, and *E. colona*. Least preferred hosts were *D. setigera*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *B. mutica*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, and *Saccharum munjo* (3.7-20.3%). ■

Predation of yellow stem borer (YSB) moths by wolf spider

E. G. Rubia, L. P. Almazan, and K. L. Heong, IIRRI

The wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* Boes. et Strand common in ricefields feeds on a variety of prey, including hoppers, collembolans, flies, and the mirid predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*. Studies have shown that the spider exhibits a functional response: consump-

Functional response of the wolf spider to yellow stem borer moths. a' = attack rate, Th = handling time.

tion of prey by individual spiders increases with prey density.

We studied the functional responses of the wolf spider to 1-d-old female YSB moths. Spiders were reared in the laboratory and starved for 3 d prior to the experiment. A spider was released in 19-cm-diam mylar cages containing 1, 2, 3, 5, or 10 moths, with five replications. Three stages of rice TN1 were used as substrates: 13- and 35-d-old plants and rice stubble.

L. pseudoannulata searched for YSB moths most efficiently on 13-d-old rice plants (see figure). At this stage, there was less foliage and the search area was smaller than on 35-d-old rice plants with more than 10 tillers and denser leaves. It is also possible that moths hide better in 35-d-old plants.

Moth consumption was lowest on rice stubble, perhaps because the color of moths and stubble looked similar to the spider. ■

Electroantennogram technique for studying olfactory sensitivity of insects to volatile compounds

R. Ramachandran and Z. R. Khan, ICIPE-IIRRI Project, IIRRI

Volatile compounds produced by plants or conspecific species may have complex effects on an insect's fitness in a given environment. Host plant-derived volatile compounds may be used by insects to colonize the plant. Compounds produced by conspecifics may be used to locate mates.

Identifying the volatile compounds mediating the interaction between an

insect and its environment may have potential in insect management strategies. However, volatile compounds produced by a plant or an insect are numerous (a rice plant may produce as many as 30 to 40 volatile compounds) and often chemically very closely related.

Identifying compounds that are biologically active requires screening a large number of compounds rapidly. Electroantennogram suits this purpose. The technique is based on the principle that biologically active volatile chemicals pass through microtubules on the antenna of the insect and bind with receptor proteins, initiating electrical reactions in the dendrites of the olfactory cells as receptor membrane depolarization.

The electroantennogram measures the sum of many olfactory receptor potentials, recorded more or less simultaneously by an electrode connected to the sensory epithelium of an insect.

The procedure involves connecting the tip and the base of an insect's antenna to a recording and a reference electrode, respectively. The electrodes are connected to an amplifier and an oscilloscope (Fig. 1). The electrodes are silver nitrate-coated silver wires placed inside glass capillaries containing a saline solution (0.1% KCl). Charcoal-filtered air generated by a pump is blown continuously over the antenna through a delivery tube.

The olfactory stimulus (pure chemicals applied on filter paper or leaves) placed in a disposable pasteur pipette is inserted into the side of the delivery tube. A calibrated amount of air is passed through the pasteur pipette for a specific period of time (usually 1 s). The air carries the odorant chemicals over the antenna. The electrical signals generated